

EXOCARDIOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS IN BOYS BORN WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECT AND HEALTHY UNDER 3 YEARS OF AGE

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Annotation: In the presented scientific work, the causes and complications of congenital heart defects in children were explained from the literature. This article provides information on the incidence of congenital heart defects among children and the risk of sympatry.

Key words: heart, EXOKG examination parameters.

Congenital heart defects are one of the main problems of modern pediatrics. [9].

Congenital heart defects are the most common group of developmental defects in children and remain the leading cause of death today. [6,3].

Cardiac evaluation, including physical examinations, has been performed for newborns after birth, but the use of ExoKG to diagnose heart attacks in newborns with asymptomatic, nonsyndromic heart murmurs is controversial. ldi [1,5].

Initial cardiac assessment for newborns includes cardiac auscultation, family history of cardiovascular disease, and pulse oximeter testing. ExoKG is performed simultaneously to evaluate the primary heart murmur [4,10]. Regardless of the low diagnostic potential, an electrocardiogram and a chest X-ray are performed as an additional assessment. [10]. This systematic examination is carried out using an ultrasound machine. Echocardiographic examination of the heart in all children is required to be performed by neonatologists [3,8].

Appropriate criteria for the use of ExoKG in children and adolescents with heart murmurs have been established [2].

Newborns with heart murmurs without syndrome will not yet have heart murmurs. Heart murmurs in newborns are one of the main symptoms of CHD. In addition, the appearance of heart murmurs in children is the main reason for consulting a doctor and further evaluation. In most cases, babies born with CHD have non-syndromic heart murmurs, and its early detection and timely treatment is a complex process [7].

Echocardiography (EXOKG) determines the standard measurements of linear, volumetric, phase indicators. The normal values of the dimensions of the heart chambers, the diameter and volume of the vessels are determined. [10].

The purpose of the study. Study of echocardiographic parameters of children from birth to 3 years with congenital heart defects in Bukhara region.

Research materials and methods

In this work, the analysis of echocardiographic examination in healthy and congenital heart defect children aged from birth to 3 years in Bukhara region is presented.

Determination of echocardiographic parameters was carried out among 26 healthy boys aged 0 to 3 years and 20 healthy boys born with congenital heart defects in Nasriddin Shams Limited Liability Company in Bukhara. Echocardiographic indicators were studied using the methodology of echocardiographic study recommended by Y.V. Reznik, G.Y. Gendlin and G.I. Storjakov ("Ehocardiography in practical cardiology" - methodical manual, 2013).

Along with the echocardiographic data of all examined children, information about them is attached: the day of the examination, the child's name, gender, date of birth (for later calculation of age with the date of examination).

Echocardiographic examination. Echocardiography is a modern and safe method of ultrasound examination of the heart. This examination is carried out for the purpose of both prevention and disease detection. No treatment is required for the patient to perform an echocardiographic examination. First of all, the sick child or person should be calm. Putting children to sleep as much as possible creates the basis for more accurate and reliable echocardiographic information. The patient is placed on a flat bed. The child's clothes are removed so that their clothes do not interfere with the examination process. Then a special gel is applied to the transducer and the heart examination begins. The inconvenience of ExoKG for the patient is the coldness of the gel and the sensor. But when examining young children and babies, they are used in a heated state so that they do not wake up.

Statistical processing of the echocardiographic data obtained in the study according to the standard deviation and representative error was carried out directly using Microsoft Office software on a Pentium-IV personal computer to determine the indices of the "STTGRAPH 5.1" program. package was implemented from the common matrix of Excel 7.0.

Research results:

Echocardiographic indicators in children are among the main indicators for assessing their physical development.

Our studies showed that aortic (AO) width varied from 9.1 mm to 12.3 mm with a mean of 11.1 ± 0.6 mm in healthy boys from birth to 1 year of age. In boys born with congenital heart defects of the same age, the width of the aorta (AO) varied from 7.1 mm to 14.0 mm, with an average of 12.1 ± 0.5 mm.

In healthy boys from birth to 1 year of age, the width of the left lobe (LV) varied from 9.1 mm to 13.0 mm, with an average of 11.2 ± 0.5 mm, the same value from birth to 1 year of age. in boys born with heart defects, the width of the left ventricle (LV) varies from 6.1 mm to 14.0 mm, with an average of 11.9 ± 0.6 mm.

Among boys of the same age, the thickness of the right ventricular (RV) wall varies from 5.0 mm to 12.0 mm, and the average is 11.0 ± 0.8 mm, boys with congenital heart defects of the same age The thickness of the wall of the right ventricle (RV) varied from 8.0 mm to 12.3 mm, and the average was 11.8 ± 0.4 mm.

In healthy boys from birth to 1 year of age, the thickness of the interventricular septum (IS) wall varied from 4.0 mm to 7.0 mm and averaged 5.1 ± 0.3 mm, the interventricular septum wall varied from 4.1 mm to 6.0 mm in boys with congenital heart defects of the same age, and was on average 5.6 ± 0.6 mm.

The same indicators showed that in healthy boys aged 1 to 2 years, the width of the aorta (AO) varied from 9.4 mm to 12.5 mm, with an average of 11.6 ± 0.6 mm. In boys born with congenital heart defects aged 1 to 2 years, the width of the aorta (AO) varied from 10.0 mm to 19.0 mm, with an average of 13.5 ± 0.5 mm.

In healthy boys aged 1 to 2 years, the width of the left ventricle (LV) varied from 9.3 mm to 14.1 mm, with an average of 12.2 ± 0.1 mm. , in boys born with congenital heart defects aged 1 to 2 years, the width of the left ventricle (LV) varies from 10.0 mm to 20.0 mm, with an average of 15.1 ± 0.2 mm.

CONCLUSION: The results of the research showed that the results of EXOKG parameters in healthy boys from birth to 3 years old were lower than the results of EXOKG in boys born with congenital heart defects of the same age.

References:

1. Muxiddinova, I. M. (2022). IMPACT OF ENERGY DRINKS AND THEIR COMBINATION WITH ALCOHOL TO THE RATS METOBOLISM. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 544-549.
2. Mukhiddinova, I. M. (2022). EFFECTS OF CHRONIC CONSUMPTION OF ENERGY DRINKS ON LIVER AND KIDNEY OF EXPERIMENTAL RATS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 6-11.
3. Muxiddinova, I. M. (2022). Effects of Energy Drinks on Biochemical and Sperm Parameters in Albino Rats. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES*, 3(3), 126-131
4. Ильясов, А. С., & Исмадова, М. М. (2022). ЖИНСИЙ АЪЗОЛАРГА ЭНЕРГЕТИК ИЧИМЛИКЛАРНИНГ САЛБИЙ ТАСИРИ. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 66-69.
5. Muxiddinova, I. M. (2022). Demage of Energy Drinks on the Spermatogenesis of Male Rat's. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 1(9), 111-118.
6. Muxiddinova, I. M. (2022). Effects of Energy Drinks on Biochemical and Sperm Parameters in Albino Rats. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES*, 3(3), 126-131.
7. Muxiddinova, I. M. (2022). Ameliorative Effect of Omega-3 on Energy Drinks-Induced Pancreatic Toxicity in Adult Male Albino Rats. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 1(5), 13-18.
8. Razokov, I. B., Rahimov, D. A., Ismatova, M. M., & Kurbonzoda, S. N. MAIN FACTORS CAUSING IRON-DEFICIENT ANEMIA IN CHILDREN OF EARLY AGES. In *SPECIAL EDITION FOR 1st BUKHARA INTERNATIONAL MEDICAL STUDENTS CONFERENCE* (p. 61).
9. Muxiddinova, I. M., & Sobirova, A. Z. (2022). Pregnancy with Twins with Preeclampsia. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 212-221.
10. Muxiddinova, I. M., & Sobirova, A. Z. (2022). Anemia Iron Deficiency in Pregnancy. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 191-199.
11. Mukhiddinova, I. M. (2022). ENERGY DRINKS MAY AFFECT THE OVARIAN RESERVE AND SERUM ANTI-MULLERIAN HORMONE LEVELS IN A RAT MODEL. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 626-632.
12. Mukhiddinova, I. M. (2023). High Caffeine Exposure Increases Ovarian Estradiol Production in Immature Rats. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 2(3), 8-11.
13. Mukhiddinova, I. M. (2023). Energy Fluids May Affect the Ovarian Reserve and Serum Anti-Mullerian Hormone Level. *Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education*, 2(5), 358-364.
14. Mukhiddinova, I. M. (2022). ENERGY DRINKS MAY AFFECT THE OVARIAN RESERVE AND SERUM ANTI-MULLERIAN HORMONE LEVELS IN A RAT MODEL. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 626-632.
15. Ихтиярова, Г. А., & Розикова, Д. К. (2023). МИКРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ С РЕПРОДУКТИВНЫМИ ПОТЕРЯМИ В АНАМНЕЗЕ. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(4), 1002-1008.

16. Salimova, T. B. (2022). Features of the Course of Pregnancy in Pregnant Women with Fetal Growth Restriction Syndrom and the Role of Doppler Velocimetry. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(6), 557-56
17. Salimova, T. B. Homila O'sishi Chegaralanishi Sindromi Bilan Homilador Ayollarda-Homiladorlikning Kechishi Va Uning Diagnostikasida Dopplerometriyaning O'rni.

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